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Planing organization of macro environment of the airports

The peculiarities of the planning organization and improvement with modern amenities of environment (macro environment) of airports that must be taken into account by strategies of development of territories and enterprises. The results of the introduction of modern practices of urban planning and marketing strategies of communication nature into the educational process are presented.

Planning, building and exploitation of airports, as air portals of the state, region, settlement, is accompanied by the decision of row of town-planning tasks, in particular, plan organization of network of passenger, freight and postal transportations, and also to equipping with modern amenities and decorative design of spaces adherent to the highways and railways [1-3].

Geographical, climatic and urbanism features of location of airport, his place in the system of transport reports, distance to the city and other urbanism factors largely influence at choice types of transport for carrying passengers, load and mail. For passengers it can be above-ground (tram, trolleybus, subway, busses, rout taxis, private and rout airplanes, propellers) travel (electric-, diesel trains, monorail pendant cabins), water transport (ferries, ships) and also modal combined transport systems.

A planning organization of a transport network related to functioning of airports must, from one side, be aimed at maximal reduction of time of connection, from other – to provide a comfort, artistic expressiveness of landscape, high level of equipping with modern amenities of transport ways. Distance of transportations and time that must be spent on a road are limited to the norms and folds 30-40 min at distance a to 30 km. Exactly these kilometers and minutes can be examined as first, that form the image of country foe tourists, guests, began to flow that considerably increases lately.

Will try to consider and analyze the urbanism constituent of transport connections of the International airport (IA) “Boryspil” with Kyiv as tourist destination. It, first of all, a question of a planning organization and equipping with modern amenities, grant of aesthetic and PR, is expressivenesses to spaces that fit closely to the network of passenger traffic of different types of transport.

Passenger transportations between IA “Boryspil” and Kyiv come true by a public (busses, rout taxis, speed line of railway that began to function from 2018) and individual motor-car (passenger and leased cars), air transport (airplanes, by propellers, service airplanes).

A road way consists of two parts:

- the entrance from an airport to crossing with the international highway of MO3 (Kyiv – Kharkiv) in a suburb Boryspil;
- the international segment of highway of MO3 long 18,5 kilometers, that conducts from Boryspil to the border of Kyiv.

The carrying capacity of six-row highway makes 40 thousand cars on twenty-four hours. A speed line of railway is “Airport “Boryspil” – Central railway station” also provides carrying passengers during the estimated time – 30-35 min. Volume of transportations only for the first three month of exploitation made 200 thousand passengers.

During building and exploitation of area of highway a natural landscape was maximally kept with the aim of creation of original “green” buffer belt long an about 20 km there. Were the envisaged safety measures in relation to the exception of possibility of exit on travel part of wild animals (reticulated metallic protection), arranged overpasses and underground passages for pedestrians – habitants of the settlement located for both sides of highway and other. On separate areas were set entrance/departure sign, typical after decision stop suburban public transport, negligible quantity decorative form (for example, a sculpture of bear is talisman of “Olympiad – 80”; a football ball is a symbol of Euro – 2012) and other.

Such decision, from one side, by means of a plan organization and equipping with modern amenities of territories with bringing in of minimum after an amount designer decision provided authentication of city as to the object of tourist visit, from other, confirmed during decades in practice with stand slogan “Kyiv is the most green megalopolis of Europe” (fig.1). The special role was here taken to the systems and receptions of planning of greenery, that interspersed with a route discolorations throughout all seasons (fig.1, d, e).

Fundamental changes in Ukraine, that occurred during Independence, resulted in strengthening of role of migratory processes in social and political life, in particular, to the increase of quantity of population of Kyiv to 7,5 million people, swift development of aviation connections and origin of new type of urban groupings – aircrafts.

Areas close to the airport are becoming in our time placed, attractive for business and tourism. They build different types of car parking and car rental, hotels, logistics centers, companies of network trade and catering, reorganized the transport network, there are, in particular, two-level solution, etc. It allows simultaneously to form and satisfy business and tourist demand, to create a corresponding positive impression on visitors of the country, to give investment attractiveness to adjoining territories, etc. [6].

The nature of the development of territories at the entrance to Kyiv also changes. City actively gets symptom modern megalopolises are multistoried dwelling and office building, network trade complexes, multilevel transport upshots etc.

At the same time, it follows to take into account that separate territories with the special ecological framework assume only the certain level of intensity of reception of tourists without negative influence on an environment (reduction of zones of natural landscape, compression of building of wayside areas, worsening of terms of residence and etc.). At state level need introduction of control system and development of mechanism of optimization of functioning of the destinations on the basis of clusterization [6].

a

b

c

d

e

Fig.1 International highway of MO3, area “Boryspil – Kyiv” [4, 5]:
 a – building period, in 1969, b – period of exploitation, in 2016;
 c – in 1975; d – in 2018; e – in 2019.

World experience of a plan organization of routes that bind airport to the megalopolises, such as Moscow, New York, Paris, Warsaw, unfortunately, gives very many negative examples. In the window of car or the trains the visitor sees everywhere building of syllables, hangars, workshops of monotonous grey color, primitive after forms and covered with drawing graffiti.

At the same time, Ukrainian specialists should study landscape architects of India (Indira Gandhi International Airport, 17 kilometers from Delhi), Azerbaijan (Baku Heydar Aliyev Airport, 17 kilometers from a city), USA (Kansas City International Airport, 36 kilometers from a city) that provided visualization of every ‘shot’ of travelling space semantically saturated artistically and informatively by expressive decisions.

Attempts to correct the sad consequences of wipeout of Ukrainian architectonically-landscape school do teachers of establishments of higher education

of Kyiv, Lviv, Kharkiv and other. In this direction it follows positive to count experience of teachers of department of town-planning of faculty of architecture, building and design of NAU, that inculcate modern world practices of town-planning and marketing strategies of communication character in an educational process [7, 8].

Considerable personal interest in this problem can be observed in the subject of coursework [8] and diploma projects, the active participation of students in interdisciplinary education events [7].

At development of general layout of settlement on 2-4 thousand habitants the students of 3th course will realize the idea of creation to the airports nearby IA "Boryspil". Project suggestions head for the decision of problems of development of region and airport, and must opinion of authors, promote them tourist attractiveness.

In diploma projects under the direction of teachers of department students are investigate the problems of a plan organization of access roads, railway station areas, pitch dominants of architecture of airports and other, suggestions are developed in relation to their decision.

Considerable attention is spared to participating of students in interdisciplinary educational events [7], general projects of Department of town-planning and architecture of Kyiv municipal state administration (KMSA) and Group of companies A+S in Ukraine, in particular, in the construction of a transport model of Kyiv [9].

Conclusions

1. Air, ground and underground transport spaces in the zones of airports must execute significant role in forming of positive image of country.

2. Planning organization and improvement of the macro-environment of airports with the use of architectural facilities allow to effectively identify the locality as a tourist destination.

3. Involvement of students and young scientists-architects of the National Aviation University to the study of world practices of town-planning and decision of strategic for a country tasks became a significant deposit in relation to forming of them professional competence.

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